

Boiled Yam Food Target Product Profile Workplan, at UAC-FSA-Benin

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Ethics: The activities, which led to the production of this document, were assessed and approved by the CIRAD Ethics Committee (H2020 ethics self-assessment procedure). When relevant, samples were prepared according to good hygiene and manufacturing practices. When external participants were involved in an activity, they were priorly informed about the objective of the activity and explained that their participation was entirely voluntary, that they could stop the interview at any point and that their responses would be anonymous and securely stored by the research team for research purposes.

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ABSTRACT

The RTBfoodomics project officially started with a kickoff and planning meeting organized at CIAT (Cali, Colombia) in March 2025. This gathering brought together the partners of the project to align on project activities and responsibilities. Defining a standard sampling protocol was of particular importance.

Following the meeting, UAC-FSA produced a detailed workplan outlining the genotypes to be harvested and the samples to be produced and analyzed. The sampling protocol was discussed at length to ensure enough replications of each genotype were included in the workplans (at planting, harvesting and sample preparation).

Boiled yam is characterized by its own intrinsic attributes preferred by consumers. Colour, crumbliness, and aroma are defined as the core traits for boiled yam, our Food Target Product Profile. A set of 24 genotypes were firstly selected to cover the range of variability coded as good, medium, and low for core each trait. These genotypes (24) were planted at Dassa (UAC_Biorave center) in 4-6 biological replications (15 plants per replication) in April 2025. Plants will be harvested at about 8-9 months of age in December 2025-January, 2026. The sampling protocol consists of taking samples based on the phenotyping of the three core traits. It is expected at least a sub-samples of 15 genotypes for the three traits. For each core trait, sample preparation is replicated 4-6 times, i.e. a total of $5 \times 3 \times (4-6)^1$ (5 genotypes x 3 levels of trait x "4-6" replicates) = 60-90 samples. Each biological replicate (block line) for each genotype will be represented by tubers produced by the 15 plants (in line) which will be harvested together on the same date. The tubers will be randomly divided into three groups. Tubers from the first group will be processed and assessed immediately after harvest (with no storage period, base line). Tubers from the second group will be processed and assessed three months after harvest. Tubers from the third group will be processed and assessed five months after harvest. The raw and boiled samples will be analysed in accordance with established SOPs, then freeze-dried for shipment to the RHUL lab, and frozen extracts using aroma trapping techniques for aroma/flavor assessment at Montpellier.

Key Words: Boiled yam, Metabolomics, Phenotyping, Genotypes, Texture, Aroma

¹ Due to the lack of seeds for some genotypes, replications vary between 4 to 6

1 PHENOTYPING SAMPLES

1.1 Phenotyping using harmonized SOPs: Core traits

Colour of fresh and boiled yam, crumbliness, and aroma of boiled yam were defined as the core traits for this Food Target Product Profile. The colour of fresh yam will be measured using a chromameter (Lab), while texture (penetration test) and sensory attributes (QDA) will be evaluated according to established phenotyping standard operating protocols (**Appendix 1**).

Additionally, the rheological properties of yam flour will be assessed using a rheometer (RVA). Based on previous studies, phenotyping will focus on these essential traits—colour, crumbliness, and aroma. An initial set of 24 genotypes was selected to ensure that at least 15 of them represent a range of variability (good, medium, and low quality) for each trait.

1.2 Phenotyping for aroma and flavor

While the aroma will be evaluated sensorially at FSA-UAC, it will also be instrumentally quantified at CIRAD (Montpellier, France). Raw and boiled yam samples will be frozen prior to shipment to CIRAD for aroma characterization.

1.3 Additional trait to phenotype (if any)

To a lesser extent, sweet taste is also considered a relevant trait. It will be characterized using a sensory panel, as described in the SOP (<https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00600>).

1.4 Environmental/physiological conditions during the phenotyping process

Yam genotypes will be harvested 8 to 9 months after planting (April to December-January), corresponding to the dry season. Currently, genotypes are being planted (end of April) at the Dassa field by breeders (Biorave). After harvest, samples of tubers from each genotype will be characterized immediately without any storage period. The remaining tubers will be stored for up to five months at the BIORAVE Center site and then characterized again to assess quality traits after storage.

2 DEFINITION OF GENOTYPES TO SCREEN.

A group of 43 yam genotypes was collected from Biorave sites (Massi, Dassa, and Djougou) and used to select 24 genotypes for metabolomics analysis. Based on the three core traits and the developed SOPs, genotypes were classified into three quality groups: good, medium, and low. The genotypes selected for planting within the RTBfoodomic project are presented in **Table 1**. Freeze-dried samples from these genotypes will be prepared for shipment to RHUL. Frozen samples will be shipped to CIRAD for the instrumental evaluation aroma and flavor.

Table 1: Genotypes selected for planting within the RTBfoodomics project.

Genotype	Nature /origin	White Colour	Aroma of yam	Crumbly
Assinaga (Dr)	Landrace	Good	Good	Good
Kpouna/Laboko (Dr)	Landrace	Good	Good	Good
TDrA5-2003	Improved-released	Good	Good	
TDa0000194	Improved variety-released	Good		
TDa1511008	Improved variety			Good
TDa1515030	Improved variety		Good	
TDr1414005	Improved variety			Medium
TDr1440045	Improved variety	Good		Medium
TDr1443002	Improved variety		Good	Low
TDa1510043	Improved variety-released	Medium	Medium	Medium
Odo (Dr)	Landrace	Medium	Medium	
TDa1508044	Improved variety		Medium	Medium
TDa1515032	Improved variety			Medium
TDr1000344	Improved variety	Medium	Medium	
TDrA39-2003	Improved variety	Medium		Low
TDa1520002	Improved variety	Medium	Low	Medium
TDr8902665	Improved variety		Medium	Low
TDa1520008	Improved variety	Low	Low	Good
TDa1520050	Improved variety-released	Low		Low
TDa1510119	Improved variety	Low	Low	
Kpèguèlèhoun (Da)	Local-released	Low	Low	
TDa1506142	Improved variety	Low		
Assoura (Dr)	Landrace		Low	
Kpotchebim (Dr)	Landrace			Low

They offer a wide variability (good, medium and low quality) for the core traits colour, crumbliness and aroma. In some cases, there is no phenotypic information regarding some of the traits. Planting will take place at Dassa field (Biorave) at end of April, 2025. Each of the 24 genotypes will be planted in six replications (15-20 plants per replication). Plants will be harvested at about 8-9 months of age in December 2025-January, 2026.

2.1 Brief description of the origin of the genotypes to screen

In some cases, the material to be screened will come from a biparental population; in others, it will consist of traditional landraces and improved varieties (some of which have been officially released). **Da** and **Dr** refer to *Dioscorea alata* and *D. rotundata* (or *D. cayenensis* subsp. *rotundata*), respectively. The improved varieties, designated as TDa and TDr, were developed at IITA-Ibadan, while the landraces are local varieties collected from farmers in Benin.

2.2 Alternative back-up germplasm or sources of sampling

Our selected genotypes are being planted (April 2025) on a plot in Dassa. In the event of any issues that may affect the availability of these genotypes, we will rely on those planted at Massi—using alternative genotypes from the same preference category available at Biorave's experimental farm. Additionally, some genotypes can be sourced from local producers who cultivate them in the same production area.

3 SAMPLING STRATEGY AND EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

Planting and harvesting each genotype will take place in a field located in Dassa. These activities will be carried out by the breeder's team from Biorave. Harvesting is scheduled for December 2025 to January 2026. Laboratory analyses will be conducted by personnel from FSA-UAC.

The sampling protocol consists of taking samples based on the phenotyping of the three core traits. For each core trait, sample preparation must be replicated six times, i.e. a total of $5 \times 3 \times 6$ (5 genotypes x 3 levels of trait x 6 replicates) = 90 samples. The raw and boiled samples will be analysed in accordance with established SOPs, then freeze-dried for shipment to the RHUL lab, and frozen samples for aroma/flavor assessment at Montpellier.

3.1 Biological replications

Ideally, six biological replications will be included in the study. For each replication, 15-20 plants (depending on availability of seeds, yield) will be randomly selected and harvested. Due to the number of genotypes (24) and to the number of replications (6) associated to lab analyses, the harvesting period will cover one to two months but in well-defined/scheduled time, between December 2025 and January 2026, with the early genotypes first. The six biological replications will thus consist of the 6 batches (**Figure 1**).

3.2 Sampling strategy.

Each biological replicate will be represented by the tubers produced by (ideally) the 15-20 plants harvested together on the same date from each genotype/replication plot (**Figure 1**). The tubers will be randomly divided into **three groups**. Tubers from the first group will be processed and assessed immediately after harvest (**with no storage period**). Tubers from

the second group will be processed and assessed **three months after harvest**. Tubers from the third group will be processed and assessed **five months after harvest**.

3.3 Handling and processing tubers.

At any given time, **tubers from up to five plants will be processed together**. Therefore, up to five tubers will be available for phenotyping and sampling (**Figure 1**). Each of these genotype **will be treated in the same way**, and the samples they produce will then be pooled together.

Figure 1: Diagram illustrating the key steps in sample preparation, processing and shipment.

Due to sampling limitations (24 genotypes x 6 replicates), harvesting period will cover one to two months but in well-defined/scheduled time, between December 2025 and January 2026, with the early genotypes first

Each biological replicate involves 15-20 plants per genotype. Tubers collected from a given replicate, in a given date will be randomly split into three groups which will be processed immediately, three months after harvest and five months after harvest, respectively. Up to five tubers will be processed per genotype together at each time.

3.4 Schematic description of sample processing and handling

Figure 1 provides a flow diagram outlining the harvesting and processing strategy. Up to five tubers per genotype will be processed together at any given time (Batch). It also gives a general description of how tubers will be handled and processed. Each batch will be split into 5 portions (**A, B, C, D** and **E**). Two of these 1/5 tuber portions (**A** and **B**) will be pooled together and homogenized. A sample of the homogenized raw tissue will be used for biochemical characterization of colour and dry matter content (**Figure 1**). A small sample of the homogenized raw tissue (e.g., 100 g) will be freeze-dried and shipped to RHUL for metabolomic analysis. Finally, a sample of the remaining raw homogenized tissue will be frozen and shipped to CIRAD for instrumental assessment of aroma and flavor (**Figure 1**).

The remaining portions (**C, D** and **E**) will be steam cooked together. Standard cooking procedures will be employed to ensure consistency. One of these cooked portions (**C**) will

be freeze-dried and shipped to RHUL for metabolomic analysis. A second cooked portion (**D**) will be frozen and shipped to CIRAD for instrumental assessment of aroma and flavour. The remaining cooked portion (**E**) will be used for Lab (instrumental color and texture profiling) and sensory evaluation at UAC-FSA (**Figure 1**).

4 CHRONOGRAM OF ACTIVITIES

Information in Table 1 and Figure 1 regarding dates of planting, harvesting, processing and sample shipment can then be integrated into a chronogram of activities through the shipment of samples to the RHUL lab. This experimental design will be replicate in 2026-2027 and 2027-2028 years.

Table 2: Tentative chronogram of activities.

Field		No storage period			Three months after harvest			Five months after harvest		
Planting	Harvest	Sensory panel	Sample shipment		Sensory panel	Sample shipment		Sensory panel	Sample shipment	
			Frozen (CIRAD)	Freeze-dried (RHUL)		Frozen (CIRAD)	Freeze-dried (RHUL)		Frozen (CIRAD)	Freeze-dried (RHUL)
End of April 2025	Dec 2025-Jan 2026	Dec 2025-Jan 2026	Feb-Mar 2026	Mar-Apr 2026	Mar-Apr 2026	May-Jun 2026	Jun-Jul 2026	May-Jun 2026	Jul-Sep 2026	Sep-Oct 2026
March 2026	Nov-Dec 2026	Jan-Feb 2027	Feb-Mar 2027	Mar-May 2027						
March 2027	Nov-Dec 2027	Jan-Feb 2028	Feb-Mar 2028	Mar-May 2028						

APPENDICE

APPENDIX 1. LINK TO PUBLISHED STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURES.

SOP for sensory characterization of boiled yam. Cotonou, Benin	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00600
SOP for sample preparation and cooking time for texture analysis of boiled yam	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00603
SOP for Sample Preparation and the Measurement of Texture of Boiled Yam	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00786